

DIFFERENT ASPECTS OF “SHOULD”, “OUGHT TO” AND “HAD BETTER”

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Abstract: The distinctions and similarities between modal verbs like "should" and "ought to" and "had better" are discussed in this article. While many people are already familiar with the word "should," fewer are aware of two other verbs that can also be used for suggestions: "ought to" and "had better." The rules for using the abovementioned modal verbs are explained separately. In addition to this, you have also clarified and provided other instances of when these modal may be used interchangeably and when they can't. As a result, I recommend that you read this article, and I hope that you really like it and gain profit from it.

Keywords: Should, ought to, had better, must, have to, shall, will, would, have to.

Introduction. Modal verbs such as "should," and "ought to," and "had better" are auxiliary verbs that express concepts like ability, advice, and obligation. They are weaker and less direct than "must" and "have to." While many people are already familiar with the word "should," fewer are aware of two other verbs that can also be used for suggestions: "ought to" and "had better." These two verbs are less common in English, but using them proficiently demonstrates a speaker's ability to use a higher-level language. What is clear is that "should" is far more common than the other two verbs, and its usage is very similar in written and spoken language. In spoken English, the phrases "ought to" and "had better" are more common.

Main part

Let's get practice giving advice! Amanda should see a doctor. This demonstrates that we believe Amanda should see a doctor.

The most common way to give advice is with the word "should." The verb "should" can express mild or forceful advice of any kind, including advice, recommendation, advisability, desirability, suggestion, obligation, duty, and responsibility. Consider the following examples:

- Shahnoza: My exam was a failure. Diyora: Really? You should study more.
- Young children should not watch violent television shows.

"Ought to" is more similar to "should" in meaning and can be used interchangeably if the action referred to is desired by the speaker. Consider the following sentences:

- Perhaps you ought to wait outside this place.
- You ought to take the day off yourself.
- There was no one around. She ought to have guessed.
- It's bitterly cold outside. -You ought to put on a warm jacket. ("Ought to" is almost never used in the negative sentences.)

You had better take it easy. You're going too fast! You'd better make sure you don't forget to buy your tuition. If you do, the university will expel you!

As you can see "had better" is a bit stronger. When we say "had better," we imply that there will be a negative consequence if we do not perform the action. It is not always

interchangeable with should in this way. It includes the concept of a warning: if you do not follow my advice, something bad will happen.

Consider the following examples: How should I pay my payments? "Should" is a requirement with no negative ramifications. In these cases, we can't use "had better." Consider the following real-life example to see the difference.

- You had better do your homework. The teacher will give you a low grade if you do not complete your homework.

It's worth noting that "you had better..." can be abbreviated to "you'd better..." This is proper grammar and is used frequently in conversation. Some native speakers say, "You better..." but this isn't correct. In proper grammar, the word "had" is required.

In the instances above, you can see that the modal verbs are followed by the plain form of the verb. Subject + modal verb + main verb +... As an example:

You should study more diligently.

You should to study more diligently. Wrong!

You'd be better being slow down. Wrong!

Remember that "ought to" is a modal verb that comes after a basic verb. The word "to" is not an infinitive.

There is also a distinction in the negative form. Only the verb "should" allows for a contraction; the other two do not. Take note of the placement of the word "not" in the negative statement below. The word "not" comes after "should" and "had better," but before "ought to" (i.e., "ought not to").

MODAL + SUBJECT + BASIC VOCABULARY +... Should I visit my parents' or friend's house?

Another distinction is that "ought to" and "had better" are not commonly used with queries.

Should I use cold water to a burn?

Ought I to apply cool water to a burn? Wrong!

Had better I apply cool water to a burn? Wrong!

WH-(information) inquiries can also be produced by placing the WH-question word right before the modal.

For example:

- What should I do about my situation?
- What should we eat for supper tonight?
- When should they contact their manager?

Many modal verbs have many meanings. When implying a likely event, for example, "should" and "ought to" have comparable meanings. However, we can express certain meanings using the modal verb "should" or the semi-modal verb "ought to" in the following ways.

1. To express a duty or recommendation.

Before dinner is ready, you should (ought to) finish your homework.

You should (ought to) exercise extra caution.

2. To express probability.

She should (ought to) be ready by now.

I really liked his initial drawing. As a result, the new one should (should) be intriguing.

Although, in general, "should" is more commonly used. "Ought to" is commonly used in speech to express obligation rather than possibility.

When we get to the conclusion that something is certain or extremely likely based on facts, we can use the word "must" but not "should" or "ought to". Examine the following phrase: She's skating for the third time this week. She must truly enjoy it.

3. When referring to what an outside authority suggests, we choose "should":

Before removing the lid, the computer should be disconnected from the power supply, according to the handbook. (rather than... ought to be disconnected...)

4. When we give counsel with the pronoun I, we use should (or would), not ought to: I should depart early tomorrow if I were you. (Or I'd leave... or I'd leave...)

5. We use should-in questions, especially when it comes to wh-questions.

What should he do if he run into any problems?

Should I call you at your house?

6. We connect "should" or "ought to" with a past participle to represent activities that did not occur in the past and for which we are sorry:

They should have waited for the rain to stop. (He apologize for not doing so.)

This pattern is frequently employed to express sorrow or criticism, and the negative words "shouldn't" or "oughtn't to have" are frequently used in this context.

7. We also use "should" or "ought to" with a past participle to show an expectation. If the airplane came on schedule, he should / ought to have arrived in Memphis early this morning.

8. We can use "should" inquiries to make proposals or to seek confirmation or advice:

Should I contact an ambulance for you?

Whom should I deliver the message to?

It's worth noting that in sentences like these, we can also use shall, which has a very similar meaning.

Compare the use of shall and should in the following sentences,

I shall read the script on the train. (Or I'll read...) I should read the script on the train tomorrow, but I'm afraid I'll be too exhausted.

9. We can use "better" instead of "should" or "ought to," especially in spoken English, to indicate that we believe it is a good idea to do something: If you're not feeling well, you had better ask Clara to accompany you instead.

(Alternatively, you should/ought to...)

Although we don't utilize it to discuss the past or make general remarks:

You should/ought to have gotten on a later train.

(not You had better have gotten...)

I don't believe parents should or ought not to have taken a later train.

(Not... parents had better take...)

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